

A BRIEF INTRODUCTION OF THE ARABIC LANGUAGE ACADEMIES-THE ROLE PLAYERS IN THE MODERNIZATION OF ARABIC LANGUAGE

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Abstract

Objective- This paper aims at introducing the role played by Arabic language Academies in modernizing Arabic language facing up to the modern challenges that Arabic language undergo in the technologically advanced modern times. It also emphasizes on the importance of unifying the efforts of Academies by making their contributions available to every Arab countries, Writers, Media and Citizens.

Design/ Methodology/ Approach- The research paper has been prepared by referring both primary and secondary sources using descriptive method

Findings- Arabic language Academies are regularizing Arabic language adding new terminologies and making the grammar easier. It thereby make Arabic remain updated.

Limitations- The political and economical tensions that exist in the Arab world were problematic in analyzing the current status Arabic language precisely. Also the number of sources required to make the research paper was not enough

Practical implications- The modernized Arabic can answer the call of modern times. Thousands of technical terms contributed by the Academies have helped the Arabic language to confront modernity. It has also opened the doors for Arabization making Arabic the language of science and technology.

Scope for future works- This area of research may help students, teachers, linguists and academicians to find the solutions that Arabic like any other language face.

Key words- Arabic Language, Arabic Language Academies, Modernity, Terminologies, Standardization

Introduction

Arabic Language Academies are the result of an idea that germinated in the minds of Arab Linguists and literary people in the nineteenth Century. When the foreign languages like English and French started intruding the Arab world, protectors of classical Arabic wanted to be attentive. It led them to establishing Arabic language academies in Arab countries in the beginning of the twentieth century. The idea was proposed by Arab governments of Syria, Egypt and Iraq etc with the goal of protecting Arabic, forming new Arabic terminologies in the various fields of science, and composing Arabic dictionaries in modern sciences. This thought strived for years until the first language Academy for Arabic was established in Syria to preserve the heritage of Arabic.

Since the establishment, the Academies have played its defining role in countries where Arabic is the mother tongue. For example, collection of Arabic language dictionaries which the Arabic language Academy in Cairo produced over the past eight decades, are a great contribution in the advancement of Arabic language. The

Ismavil. M Edavarad / A Brief Introduction of The Arabic Language Academies-The Role Players In The Modernization of Arabic Language

Academy has been awarded prize by the Egyptian government for this effort. Today there are many Arabic language academies throughout the Arab world. French language Academy, founded in 1635 with the goal of prescribing rules for the French language in order to purify it and make it capable of treating the Arts and Sciences was the inspiration behind this idea.¹

Today there are many other Arabic Language Academies in the Arab world. Many Arab countries have established their own Language academies understanding its importance. These academies are The Arabic Language Academy of Syria established in 1919, The Arabic Language academy of Cairo established in 1932, The Iraqi Language Academy, established in 1974, The Jordan Academy established in 1976, and Academies in Tunisia, Israel, Mecca-Saudi Arabia, Sudan, Libya, Algeria and Palestine etc. Unfortunately, the Academies of Libya and Algeria are not functioning at the moment. A brief detail of the major Arabic Language academies, is given below.

Academy of Arabic language- Syria

As pointed above, the first academy of Arabic language was established in 1919 in Damascus, capital of Syria. It remained as noted by the Encyclopedia Britannica, the bastion of Arabic Language working both to preserve and modernize the language throughout the 96 years.² It started comprising of eight members with certain tasks assigned to them which includes considering the further improvement of Arabic and inspecting its current status, spreading Arabic literature, publishing and preserving the Arabic manuscripts, Arabising the modern scientific books written in European languages and composing books in Arabic Language on a wide range of subjects in a new pattern.

The Academy contributed to the enhancement of Arabic proposing two committees: 1) A language and literature committee responsible for all research works, means of development in Arabic Language and literature. 2) An Arts and Science committee to contribute in the expansion of Arts and Science subjects in Syria.

The Academy of Arabic Language-Cairo

The Second and the most important one among these Academies is the Language Academy of Arabic-Cairo. It was established in 1932 in Cairo, capital of Egypt. The purpose of the academy as the decree stated was as follows:

- 1) Protect the integrity of Arabic Language, and make use of Arabic perfect and compatible with the demands of the progress made in the Science and the Arts, join hands with the needs of modernity composing dictionaries, interpreting old terminologies or by any possible means in language.
- 2) Conduct a research on modern Arabic usages in Egypt and other Arab countries.
- 3) Explore everything which is helpful in the advancement of Arabic language after an official decree by the state.
- 4) Compile a historical dictionary of the Arabic language and organize academic studies of modern Arabic dialects.

The first one who talked about establishing a language academy in Egypt was Abdullah al Nadeem. He conveyed his concerns about it in "Tankith wa Tabkit, a newspaper published from Alexandria -Egypt in 1881. But his idea was not accepted until a group of Arabic scholars rose into occasion under the leadership of Abdullah Fikri in 1888. But they also failed in their mission due to some technical problems. In the year 1309 an

¹) Spolsky 2004:64

²) Encyclopedia Britanica (<http://www.britannica.com/EBchecked/topic/1444670/Arabic-Language-Academy-of-Damascus>)

Academy was established in Egypt, but it no longer existed as its motive was to write Arabic in colloquial language.

In 1907 Darul Uloom club was established in Cairo under the leadership of Muhammad Hafni Nasif. After a series of discussions the club members came to the conclusion that “In Arabic language a research will be done on every modern names in any way possible in the language, and when it becomes difficult a Non-Arabic word will be placed after editing and paying attention to Arabic grammar rules.

The Academy was named The Language Academy of Arabic Cairo after Egyptian revolution in 1955. Since its establishment it has contributed a lot for the enhancement of Arabic composing dictionaries in various fields of modern science and publishing books on wide variety of subjects. In Cairo Academy, the members from around the region attempt to unify their fatwas on new word and concepts entering the language. Their purist theory continues to demand that foreign loan words be replaced with pure Arabic forms. But they have had only limited success, and the result has been a multiplicity of words for one idea.³ The Arabic Language Academy of Cairo has until now published around 25 dictionaries in Arabic Language. It consists of almost all branches of science and technology.

Jordan Academy of Arabic

“The idea of founding the Jordan Academy of Arabic originated as early as the first years of the founding of the Emirate of Transjordan in the third decade of the twentieth century”⁴. The news of founding was published in The Journal of the Arab Scientific Academy in Damascus in January, 1924 issue. The Jordan Academy of Arabic is really the second Academy founded in the Arab world after the establishment of Damascus Academy. But the poor economic state and the limited availability of scientific and human resources caused it declining.

But later on, in 1976 a royal decree founding Jordan Academy of Arabic was issued and officially assumed its responsibilities on the first of October 1976 with the purpose of serving Arabic and filling the gap in the educational service in many aspects of teaching Arabic language, and joined the Cairo-based Union of Arab Scientific and Language Academies in 1977. It also promoted international and inter cultural understanding. The academy has a wide range of courses and programs run for the over all progress of the Arabic students in the country.

The Supreme Council of the Arabic language- Algeria

The Supreme Council of the Arabic language in [Algeria](#) is an advisory body to the President of the Republic of Algeria. It was established on December 21, 1996 and is working to upgrade the [Arabic language](#) and their uses in Algeria.

The Iraqi Academy of Sciences

“The Iraqi Academy of Sciences is an academy in Baghdad founded in 1948 in order to develop and regulate the Arabic language in Iraq and the Arab world. The Academy also has two other departments to regulate and develop Kurdish and Aramaic (Syriac) in Iraq, those two departments were founded in 1963. It was looted during 2003 Iraq war”⁽⁵⁾.

³) Popular Culture in the Arab world: Arts, Politics and Media-Andrew Hammond- Page: 62

⁴) Official website of Jordan Academy of Arabic(www.majma.org.jo)

⁵) Official website of Iraq Academy (<http://www.iraqacademy.iq/>)

Arabic Language Academy of Israel.

“The idea for an Israeli Arabic Language Academy emerged from a cadre of intellectuals from Haifa and Nazreth that sought to create an institution that would guide the Arabic Language in Israel and would be a compass for it like a ship sailing in stormy waters”

The Lebanese Academy of Sciences was established in August 2007 in the Republic of Lebanon followed by a decree. Its mission is not

Aims and roles of Arabic Language Academies

“The main purpose of all the Arabic Academies are the preservation of the Arabic Language and the development of Arabic to meet the needs of modern society in all domains of human knowledge”⁶ But in the beginning their focus was limited in Arabising and interpreting cultural words and terms without paying any attention to the modernization of scientific terminologies in Arabic even when it was the most important matter in the era of technological development.

When the first modern Arab state, the Arab Kingdom of Syria led by Faisal bin Hussein was established in 1920, there was an overwhelming demand for modernizing the old records and registers of the government and updating the style and contents of it. The government sent all the records with them to this newly established Academy for its suggestions and valuable opinions over the documents and gained positive response for all queries. The Academy, after reviewing the documents and carrying out a comprehensive assessment on the terminologies received from different departments and institutions such as police, health, Bank and the Municipality, paid a strong attention towards modernizing it. Then it agreed with some of the terminologies and suggested changes in some other for the better.

For the last one century the Arabic language Academy of Damascus has carried out hundreds of research on various words and terminologies in Arabic. But it is noteworthy that most of these new names which were selected by the Academy seem not better than old names. For example the word (Nafia) which is an original Arabic word, was replaced by (Deewan Amair) which no longer existed anywhere in the Arabic books. But when this replacement was not gained acceptance by any source the word was replaced by a new word (Muwasalat). The word (Dowriya) which has been in use until today was replaced by (Asas), but remained unacceptable.

Also“Arab academies have played a large role in the standardization of modern written and formal Arabic to an extend that today throughout the Arab world there is more or less one modern standard variety. This is the variety used in newspapers, newsreel broadcasting, educational books, official and legal notices, academic materials, and instructional texts of all kinds. The three academies that have had the greatest influence are those based in Cairo, Damascus and Baghdad”⁷

But it is miserable that even when these academies work “here also the linguistic activity is very academic and does not really solve real life problems. Though the academies publish dictionaries as well as some linguistic journals and their meetings, protocols, these publications largely remain in libraries and not many of their innovations are accepted for daily use”⁸ This situation leads the journals, newspapers, channels, writers, publishers and officials as well as common people to using Arabic as they like without lexical unification of terminologies. Therefore the language users of different Arab countries face hardships to understand many terms each other.

⁶) Sawaie 1986: 57, 2006

⁷) Abdul Aziz-1986, 17

⁸) Tej K, Bhatia, William C. Ritichie- The Handbook of Bilingualism Page: 850

Sometimes the politics also make things very difficult. “It is generally noticed that most of the joined or unified efforts are often handicapped by political differences. For instance there has been a pressing need for a Pan Arab Academy to coordinate the efforts of all individual academies. A proposal for establishing such an Academy was brought before a meeting of education ministers in Cairo in 1953. The same proposal was brought up several times at several meetings after that (See Chejne 1969), but it was not until 1970 that a Union of Arab Academies was established. Yet its activities were interrupted more than one time resulting in temporal suspensions of these activities due to political differences”⁹

Conclusion

This research paper is concluded stating that although there are difficulties, Arabic has now become the Language of science and technology. It can now be used to teach any branch of science, and the Arabic Language Academies have played in this regard a very crucial role.

⁹) Khalifa 1987

Ismavil. M Edavarad / A Brief Introduction of The Arabic Language Academies-The Role Players In The Modernization of Arabic Language

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Books

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